

Rudimentary Exploration of the Concept of Action from Abstract Algebra and Basic Ring Theory aimed at Postulating Post-Quantum Computing Methods through Manipulation of Unknown Quantities as Applied to the Basic Concepts of Variables and Equations

Arghya Ray, Livingston Research, Kiev and Allahabad State University, Allahabad
ORCID iD <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6926-0546>

In this research paper, we explore the possibilities associated with solving equations for variables, starting off at the most basic monomial expressions. However, analyzing the various definitions of the term ‘variable,’ it can be deduced that no single definition is sufficient to suffice the needs of compiling all possible solutions for a variable at one place, given that the equation in question is observed and operated using a combination of computational mathematics and abstract algebra. Although there is sufficient scientific literature available on applications of abstract algebra and ring theory in this field, solving for variables that logically represent unknown quantities has remained a relatively neglected area of study. Moreover, in this paper, the notions of mathematical operation and group action have been used almost interchangeably, which may not be agreed upon by the conventional academic system. The paper finally aims at developing postulates over the progress of computational mathematics, with special stress on machine learning, beyond the scope of quantum computing and related sciences.

Keywords: variables, abstract algebra, group action, unknown quantity, computation, quantum computing, digital computing

In mathematics, we generally use variables as expressions that represent an unknown value during the course of solving an equation. Nevertheless, this may not be the case always, but generally variables are used to represent the unknown value inside one or more equations that are to be solved.

In computer science, the term variable has got a special meaning, which is analogous with that as held in the general sense of mathematics too. It is explained in the following words:

“Variables are used to store information to be referenced and manipulated in a computer program. They also provide a way of labelling data with a descriptive name, so our programs can be understood more clearly by the reader and ourselves. It is helpful to think of variables as containers that hold information. Their sole purpose is to label and store data in memory. This data can then be used throughout your program.” (Launch School, 2021)

In academic sense, where basic mathematics is the mainstay, definition of variable can be simpler. That is all again is being explained in the following words:

“In Maths, a variable is an alphabet or term that represents an unknown number or unknown value or unknown quantity. The variables are specially used in the case of algebraic expression or algebra. ... Making arithmetical calculations with variables as though they were express numbers permits one to take care of scope of issues in a solitary calculation. An ordinary illustration is a quadratic recipe, which allows one to explain each quadratic condition by just substituting the numerical estimations of the coefficients of the offered condition to the variables that speak to them.” (BYJU’s Classes, 2021)

The semantics of both the aforementioned definitions are worrisome. Both of these definitions recreate variables as a multidimensional conception in the case we start dealing with polynomial functions unlike just equations in general sense. Modification of a polynomial function into an equation is not always a very easy task to do since there are identities that may even get accidentally implemented while putting an “equal to” sign following a function, which in turn might again be followed by some kind of algebraic expression. The apprehension of such symbolic representations may be modified into thinking of a matrix of possible results that have got increased possibilities while handling quadratic expressions, modulus functions, simultaneous equations, etc.

And at the introductory stages of this paper, we get starting off with a concept of sub-variable trifurcation. It means that if we have an unknown quantity that is being contained in the variable x (say, a logic symbol), then it can be trifurcated in at least three solutions capable of mapping on to three sub-variables (one or more of which can be entirely non-existent). One will be associated with being positive, one will be associated with being negative, and the one will be associated with being indeterminate. Combining the three, we can also develop the ambit of invariant in a sense of the self-destruction of the variable x , which we have just begun with.

Now if an equation is linear and has got a single solution, then can we say that it is an equation containing a variable? A variable is generally represented as x , y , or z . But is it the case with a linear equation with a single solution? Definitely not, it is not the case; even if we cannot technically say that such a variable cannot be an unknown quantity, we have to admit that such a variable must show a single value after we solve the equation.

Now let’s consider observing a linear equation with a single solution. For example, we consider the following:

$$X + 5 = 10$$

$$\text{Or } x = 10 - 5$$

$$\text{Or } x = 5$$

Now in the above equation, since all the other expressions which have been used to write it down are all decipherable and known (in that sense) quantities, is the value of ‘ x ’ unknown?

It is just waiting to be solved, not unknown. And also it cannot be described as a variable. Since the value of ‘x’ is only going to be a single value, it can be an ‘unknown’ thing at best. It cannot be a ‘variable’ thing. Even if in the language of mathematics an expression (say x, y, or z, whatever) can be an ‘unknown’ and a ‘variable’ at the same time, it cannot practically be regarded as such inside the ambit of a linear monomial function.

In the more specific language of abstract algebra, the logical understanding of the circumstances as described insofar can be semantically explained as that it knocks the preliminary boundaries of the invariant theory. A primitive demonstration of invariant theory emerge from computing the so-called invariant monomials that can be extracted from a ‘group action,’ roughly similar with the concept of arithmetical operation (far more complex and probabilistically distributed although). And from the perspective of ring theory, this situation is still impressively explained in the words of Kraft and Procesi (1996, p. 2):

“There is another way to describe the invariant ring. For this we consider the following linear action of G on the coordinate ring $K[W]$, generalizing the dual representation on the linear functions: $(g, f) \rightarrow gf, gf(w) := f(g^{-1}w)$ for $g \in G, f \in K[W], w \in W$. This is usually called the regular representation of G on the coordinate ring. (The inverse g^{-1} in this definition is necessary in order to get a left-action on the space of functions.) Clearly, a function f is invariant if and only if it is a fixed point under this action, i.e., $gf = f$ for all $g \in G$. This explains the notation $K[W]^G$ for the ring of invariants. Moreover, it follows from the definition that the subspaces $K[W]_d$ are stable under the action. Hence, the invariant ring decomposes into a direct sum $K[W]^G = \bigoplus_d K[W]_d^G$ and thus is a graded K -algebra, too.”

Now putting the concepts of abstract algebra, ring theory, and K -algebra, it becomes clear that the concept of monomial functions, if it is having a single variable in its hold, is based on simple operations analogous to ‘addition’ and ‘multiplication’ (which will be reversed in the case of doing a ‘subtraction’ or a ‘division’ respectively) leading to the conception of ‘linear action’ to be applied practically.

In sum, the theory of invariant is needed to assess the position of an unknown quantity, generally called a ‘variable’ and denoted by x, y, or z, in developing the basic understanding of the semantic of the term ‘value.’ Validity is to be derived from plausible values, and except for the things like complex numbers or pie functions, this kind of algebraic approach may appear to be hazy but pragmatic at the same time.

Now, the problem is that, the concept of ‘invariant’ has never been used to directly attribute the basics of Boolean algebra. The following introductory explanation can itself be regarded as an invariant conception in its little entirety:

“As well as the logic symbols “0” and “1” being used to represent a digital input or output, we can also use them as constants for a permanently “Open” or “Closed” circuit or contact respectively. ... The variables used in Boolean Algebra only have

one of two possible values, a logic “0” and a logic “1” but an expression can have an infinite number of variables all labelled individually to represent inputs to the expression. For example, variables A, B, C etc, giving us a logical expression of $A + B = C$, but each variable can ONLY be a 0 or a 1.” (Aspen Core, 2021)

And the above example (as given in the aforementioned quotation) is again a basic reorientation of the same problem.

If $A + B = C$, and further if A can be ‘either 1 or 0,’ B can be ‘either 1 or 0,’ and C can be ‘either 1 or 0’ as well, then what will be the value of C when both $A = 1$ and $B = 1$?

Boolean algebra may have its own rules to explain the above debacle, but our approach is not going to replicate them. In such a scenario, we would say that C can be either 1 or 0 ... and both at the same time! And there is a fourth possibility too ... C can be given the form of a string consisting of logic symbols denoting one plus one (if that be the case at some instance) equal to 10_2 i.e. the binary representation of the value ‘2.’

Generalizing the above statement, we can say that we can use a ‘logic’ symbol, or a so-called ‘variable’ or ‘unknown’ expression, to represent at least four numerical (or quantitative) situations:

[1.1] 1 ... Or existing (one possibility at a time)

[1.2] 0 ... Or non-existing (one possibility at a time)

[2] \oplus ... Or analogous to ‘1’ and ‘0’ at the same time, and

[3] A variable function in binary form (possibly having finite number of many possibilities at the same time)

In digital (or classical) computing, we have seen the binary system. In quantum computing, we have seen the introduction of qubits. The advent of quantum computing vis-à-vis classical computing is being explained as the following:

“The technology of quantum computers is very different. For operation, quantum computer uses quantum bits (qubits). Qubit has a quaternary nature. Quantum mechanics’ laws are completely different from the laws of a classical physics. A qubit can exist not only in the states corresponding to the logical values 0 or 1 as in the case of a classical bit, but also in a superposition state. A qubit is a bit of information that can be both zero and one simultaneously (Superposition state). Thus, a computer working on a qubit rather than a standard bit can make calculations using both values simultaneously.” (Swami and Gill, 2011, p. 1)

Therefore, if we dare to imagine beyond, then what is going to be the next futuristic generation of computing, in the aforementioned terms? At present, it is generally believed

that we are living in the age of fifth generation computers. The next generation to come will be the sixth generation, which is posed to have nanotechnology-based quantum computing at its core (Kesharwani, 2020). Nevertheless, at least in accordance with the semantics of a combination of Boolean, abstract, and K- algebras along with application of ring theory, it can be stated that a seventh generation computer is already peeping from the horizon. What would it look like? Or what would its system of logic or hardware engineering be like? Plausibly, the logic symbols for such machinery would be based on a dynamic stringing of the different qubit-like pieces of variably multiple information and belief systems. This stringing would still involve binary values denoting the ‘power supply on’ and ‘power supply off’ gradients, nothing in between.

If the aforementioned idea be attributed to the possible seventh generation computing, then eighth generation computing would become a reality when a state of mechanical consciousness in-between ‘power on’ and ‘power off’ situations will be practically implemented. Substantially fast signaling pulses of On/Off instruction strings would involve sending alternating situations of being ‘powerful’ and ‘powerless’ in infinitesimally quick succession.

Returning to the original discussion on variables, these categories of symbolic representations are first of all to be determined as whether or not being attributes their own selves. In other words, we should ask the question, “Are variables mere containers?” And if a variable is a mere container, then what exactly is to be contained in it? The unknown may not be completely unknown. For example, if we know that the answer to a quadratic equation will contain two values, then the variable is only partly unknown. As an instance, consider the following quadratic equation:

$$X^2 - 9 = 0$$

The above quadratic equation can be solved for a set of solutions containing two values for the variable x, viz. +3 and -3; and therefore even if we don’t know the numerical quantities of a potential solution, we can still say that there would be two solutions ... and even we can say that one of them will be a positive quantity and the other one will be a negative quantity. In such a state of affair, the degree of uncertainty appears to be partially restricted.

Now imagining, with reference to the same quadratic conception, a situation where all the two solutions would be existent simultaneously. That is, value of x would be +3 and -3 at the same time (as shown in the aforementioned quadratic equation). Is this a concept similar to the superposition characteristics of a qubit? And if that be so, then what about the equations that can be written in index powers beyond 2?

For instance, how many possibilities can generally be associated with solution sets of equations that are beyond the index power of 2?

Let’s consider the following case:

$$X^3 - 27 = 0$$

$$\text{Or } x^3 = 27$$

$$\text{Or } x = 3$$

The above equation-circumstance can be restated as the following too:

$$X^3 - 27 = 0$$

$$\text{Or } x^2 \cdot x - 27 = 0$$

$$\text{Or } x^2 = 27/x$$

$$\text{Or } x^2 = 27/3 = 9$$

$$\text{Or } x = +3 \text{ and } -3$$

And in this sense, can one say that there are actually three solutions to the equation going up to cubes beyond squares? In this case, the solution set would contain $x = +3, -3,$ and $3'$, in which we say that $3'$ is itself a partially superposed entity which can be detected but whose positivity or negativity is undermining in a strict sense. Nevertheless, if $3'$ is assumed to be positive, then we must have $+3 * -3 * 3' = -27$, which was not the case with the equation we started with.

The above analysis may be interpreted as an unscientific approach, given that the conventional mathematical accuracy of the aforementioned line of thought and calculation may appear to be basically misplaced. Nevertheless, assuming the mystery remains unsolved as far as the question of having a number in multiple orientations at the same time, let's assume that a number can remain in three states, all simultaneously. In other words, say that a variable can have three values (or three varieties of values). Now, let's precede to trifurcate such a variable into three sub-variables that would give rise to a supposed polynomial. Sub-variable trifurcation may be a new concept and term altogether, which implicates that a variable x simultaneously exists in the states of high positiveness (x^p), high negativeness (x^n), and high indeterminateness (x').

Now, solution set of such a variable (inside an arbitrary equation) can be expressed as a polynomial in the course of its solving, and it can be written down as the function $f(x^p, x^n, x')$. Here, the 'course of solving' is somewhat analogous with the term 'action' in abstract algebra (Snellman, 2019). And with regard to understanding the mathematical circumstance (we just created with the help of our sub-variable trifurcation concept), we can deploy a theoretical method to compound together the innumerable possibilities in association with the above line of thought and calculation, aided by the suggestive technique as quoted below:

“However, if the mystery function $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ can be found to have simplifying properties, it may be possible to transform it into one or more simpler mysteries that can be more easily solved. To search for such properties, we need to be able to evaluate f at points $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ of our choosing where we typically have no data. For example, to test whether a function f has translational symmetry, we need to test if $f(x_1, x_2) = f(x_1 + a, x_2 + a)$ for various constants a , but if a given data point has its two variables separated by $x_2 - x_1 = 1.61803$, we typically have no other examples in our dataset with exactly that variable separation.” (Udrescu and Tegmark, 2020, p. 3)

This approach exists, and it goes further in the field of machine learning as compared with the theoretical ambit of quantum computing. In other words, and as a corollary, although quantum computing has a theory that does not directly hint towards a more mysterious mathematical (or more precisely, algebraic) computational theory, a theoretical framework to amalgamate the various possibilities associated with the notion ‘solving for x ’ clearly indicates the very existence of a next-level computational development theory that is going to be heavily dependent on the materialization of machine learning at its fullest.

A corollary from the above discussion can be stated as that every unknown quantity remains indeterminate even after solving for it, since in essence the logic symbol representing such quantity would finally exist as an invariant and not as a variable at all. This opens the path of the postulation of algebraic relativism.

Another corollary can be stated as that the assignment, existence, declaration, or identification of a variable is actually a state of ‘false positive’ since once it is held that a given variable would be representing some unknown quantity, then the very notion itself becomes an invariant for the equation in question and the rest of the mathematical operations concerned.

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